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Public Sector Governance and the Misappropriation of Tax Revenue in Nigeria

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Abstract

Public sector governance plays a critical role in ensuring the effective management of tax revenue for national development. However, in Nigeria, weak governance structures, corruption, and lack of accountability have resulted in the widespread mismanagement and misappropriation of tax revenue, thereby undermining economic growth and public trust in the state and its institutions. This study examines the relationship between public sector governance and the mismanagement of tax revenue in Nigeria, with a focus on identifying the key factors responsible for financial leakages within the system. Adopting a qualitative research approach, data were collected primarily from secondary sources, including government reports, audit reports, policy documents, legislative records, publications of anti-corruption agencies, and relevant academic literature. These data were systematically analyzed using thematic and content analysis, which enabled the identification of recurring governance-related challenges influencing tax revenue management. The study reveals that weak

institutional frameworks, lack of transparency, political interference, inadequate accountability mechanisms, and ineffective regulatory oversight are central to the misappropriation of tax revenue in Nigeria. The findings further demonstrate that the mismanagement of tax revenue has adversely affected infrastructure development, the provision of social services, and overall economic stability. The study concludes that strengthening governance mechanisms, through enhanced fiscal transparency, institutional reforms, and empowered anti-corruption agencies, can significantly reduce revenue leakages. It therefore recommends comprehensive policy reforms aimed at promoting accountability, enforcing strict tax administration regulations, and leveraging digital technologies to improve revenue monitoring and management. Ultimately, the study contributes to the broader discourse on good governance and sustainable public finance management in Nigeria.

Keywords: Public Sector Governance, Tax Revenue, Misappropriation, Corruption, Transparency, Nigeria

Introduction

Taxation is a fundamental tool for economic development and governance, providing the government with the necessary revenue to finance public expenditures, including infrastructure, healthcare, education, and social services. In Nigeria, tax revenue is derived from multiple sources, with the Pay As You Earn (PAYE) system serving as a major contributor. PAYE is a tax mechanism through which employers deduct personal income tax from employees' earnings and remit it to the relevant tax authorities. Governed by the Personal Income Tax Act (PITA) (2011) and administered by the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS), the PAYE system ensures that tax obligations are fulfilled at the point of income

distribution. In 2022, PAYE revenue stood at ₦1.53 trillion, reflecting its significance in Nigeria's tax framework (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2023).

Apart from PAYE, the Nigerian government generates substantial revenue from various tax and non-tax sources. Oil revenue, which has historically been the mainstay of Nigeria's economy, generated approximately ₦11.1 trillion in 2023. However, fluctuations in global oil prices and governance inefficiencies continue to hinder optimal utilization of these funds (NBS, 2023). The government also relies on Company Income Tax (CIT), which contributed approximately ₦3.86 trillion in 2023, and Value Added Tax (VAT), which accounted for ₦3.04 trillion within the same period (FIRS, 2023). Customs and excise duties from imported and locally manufactured goods added ₦2.7 trillion, while stamp duties and other levies contributed about ₦640 billion (NBS, 2023).

Despite these significant revenue inflows, Nigeria continues to face challenges related to the misappropriation and mismanagement of tax funds, largely due to corruption, weak institutional frameworks, and poor fiscal discipline. Corruption remains a major impediment to effective public finance management, with various reports by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and Transparency International (TI) highlighting cases of large-scale diversion of public funds. In 2022, the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) uncovered over ₦49 billion in fraudulent salary payments made to ghost workers across different government ministries (ICPC, 2022). Payroll fraud, where fictitious employees are inserted into government salary databases, significantly reduces the funds available for developmental projects.

Extravagant government spending also contributes to the mismanagement of tax revenue. A large portion of public funds is allocated to excessive allowances, inflated contracts, and luxury expenditures for political officeholders, rather than being channeled into critical sectors such as healthcare and education (BudgIT, 2023). The lack of transparency in financial management further exacerbates this issue, as weak accountability mechanisms allow public officials to mismanage funds without consequence. In many cases, budget allocations fail to align with actual expenditures, making it difficult to track the proper utilization of tax revenue (World Bank, 2023).

The consequences of these governance failures are evident in Nigeria's poor infrastructure, underfunded hospitals and schools, and persistent economic instability. Despite the enormous tax revenue collected, millions of Nigerians lack access to basic amenities such as stable electricity, potable water, and quality education. The inability of the government to properly manage public funds has resulted in widespread poverty and declining trust in state institutions. To address this issue, Nigeria must adopt comprehensive reforms that promote accountability, fiscal discipline, and transparency in public sector governance. Strengthening anti-corruption agencies such as the EFCC, ICPC, and the Office of the Auditor-General is crucial to ensuring effective oversight of public funds. Additionally, the implementation of e-governance systems, digital tax collection platforms, and real-time financial reporting mechanisms can help minimize human interference and reduce opportunities for corruption. Public engagement and awareness campaigns should also be encouraged to educate citizens on the importance of tax accountability and governance reforms.

Ultimately, taxation remains a vital component of Nigeria's economic development, but its effectiveness is undermined by poor governance and financial mismanagement. Without strong institutions, strict enforcement of public finance laws, and enhanced fiscal transparency, tax revenue will continue to be misappropriated, leaving the nation's economy in a state of perpetual decline. This study examines the intersection between public sector governance and tax revenue misappropriation in Nigeria, shedding light on the structural weaknesses in financial management and proposing solutions for sustainable and transparent fiscal policies.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

The misappropriation of tax revenue and the challenges of public sector governance in Nigeria have attracted significant scholarly attention from academics, policymakers, and international development institutions. Existing literature generally agrees that taxation remains a critical pillar of public finance, providing governments with the resources required for infrastructure development, social service delivery, and economic stabilization. Musgrave and Musgrave (1989) conceptualize taxation as serving three major functions: revenue generation, income redistribution, and macroeconomic stabilization. The effectiveness of a tax system, however, is largely dependent on administrative efficiency, equity, and institutional capacity, as emphasized by Torgler (2007). In Nigeria, tax revenue is generated from multiple sources, including Personal Income Tax under the Pay As You Earn (PAYE) system, Value Added Tax, Company Income Tax, Customs and Excise Duties, and Petroleum Profits Tax (FIRS, 2023). Despite the diversity and potential strength of these revenue sources, the country continues to experience significant governance-related challenges that undermine transparency, accountability, and effective utilization of tax proceeds.

Public sector governance broadly refers to the institutional arrangements, processes, and mechanisms through which public resources are managed and public authority is exercised (World Bank, 2017). Good governance is commonly associated with transparency, accountability, rule of law, and administrative efficiency, while weak governance environments are often characterized by corruption, poor regulatory oversight, and financial mismanagement. Nigeria's public sector governance framework has frequently been described as weak, owing to bureaucratic inefficiencies, limited institutional autonomy, political interference, and pervasive corruption (Transparency International, 2023). These governance deficiencies create fertile ground for the misappropriation of tax revenue, particularly within tax administration institutions responsible for collection, remittance, and monitoring.

The PAYE system, which constitutes a major component of Personal Income Tax in Nigeria, is designed to ensure efficient and predictable tax collection through employer-based deductions at source. While theoretically effective, empirical studies suggest that the system has been compromised by widespread revenue leakages. Ofoegbu, Akwu, and Oliver (2016) identify practices such as payroll manipulation, ghost workers, and fraudulent remittance of deducted taxes as major sources of revenue loss within the PAYE framework. Evidence from anti-corruption agencies further supports this claim, as the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission reported large-scale payroll fraud within public institutions, leading to losses exceeding ₦49 billion in 2022 alone (ICPC, 2022). These challenges are compounded by the continued reliance on manual or semi-digital tax administration systems in many states, which increases opportunities for diversion and weakens monitoring mechanisms (Okonjo-Iweala, 2021). In response, international institutions such as the World Bank (2023) have consistently advocated for comprehensive

digitalization of tax administration and routine payroll audits as strategies for minimizing revenue leakages.

Corruption remains a central theme in the literature on tax revenue misappropriation in Nigeria. Uchenna and Agbasi (2018) demonstrate that embezzlement, bribery, contract inflation, and abuse of tax exemptions significantly reduce the volume of revenue available for public expenditure. Several high-profile cases prosecuted by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission reveal patterns of illegal diversion of tax revenue through fraudulent tax waivers and misapplication of funds earmarked for infrastructure development (EFCC, 2023). The persistence of these practices has been attributed to weak institutional oversight, limited enforcement capacity, and political interference in regulatory processes (World Bank, 2020). Obayelu (2022) further argues that the opacity surrounding budget implementation and public expenditure creates opportunities for public officials to divert tax revenue with minimal accountability. Despite the presence of multiple anti-corruption agencies, their effectiveness has been constrained by political influence and limited operational independence, thereby weakening deterrence (Transparency International, 2023).

The consequences of poor public sector governance and tax revenue misappropriation are most visible in Nigeria's persistent public service delivery deficits. Studies consistently show that mismanaged tax revenue contributes directly to deteriorating infrastructure, underfunded education and healthcare systems, and inadequate social welfare programs (BudgIT, 2023). Although Nigeria reportedly generated over ₦20 trillion in tax revenue in 2023, basic public infrastructure such as road networks, electricity supply, and healthcare facilities remain grossly inadequate (NBS, 2023). Adedokun (2021) attributes this paradox to weak fiscal discipline and lack of transparency in expenditure allocation and implementation. Budget tracking reports

further reveal discrepancies between approved allocations and actual disbursements, particularly in critical sectors. For instance, only about 67 percent of the education budget allocated in 2022 was reportedly utilized, with the remainder unaccounted for (BudgIT, 2023). These governance failures have manifested in frequent industrial actions by university lecturers, poorly equipped hospitals, and declining public confidence in state institutions.

The theoretical explanations for these governance failures are well articulated in the literature. Agency Theory, as advanced by Jensen and Meckling (1976), provides a useful lens for understanding tax revenue misappropriation in Nigeria by highlighting the principal–agent problem between citizens and public officials. In contexts where monitoring and accountability mechanisms are weak, public officials entrusted with managing tax revenue may pursue personal interests at the expense of public welfare. Public Choice Theory (Buchanan, 1986) complements this perspective by suggesting that political and bureaucratic actors often behave as self-interested agents, prioritizing rent-seeking and political survival over efficient resource allocation. This helps explain the diversion of tax revenue toward politically motivated projects rather than essential public services. Institutional Theory (North, 1990) further emphasizes the role of strong, stable institutions in shaping economic performance, arguing that countries with robust tax systems, independent oversight bodies, and effective enforcement mechanisms are better able to minimize revenue misappropriation.

In line with these theoretical insights, several policy-oriented studies propose reforms aimed at strengthening tax governance in Nigeria. The International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2022) underscores the importance of deploying real-time digital tax tracking systems and integrating revenue databases across government agencies to reduce leakages. Similarly, the OECD (2023) advocates greater public participation in

budget monitoring and improved transparency in the allocation and utilization of tax revenue. Empirical studies such as Adebayo (2022) further argue that enhancing the autonomy of anti-corruption agencies, enforcing strict penalties for tax-related offences, and improving public financial reporting standards are critical for strengthening accountability.

Overall, the literature reveals a strong consensus that Nigeria's challenges with tax revenue misappropriation are deeply rooted in weak public sector governance structures. While the country possesses significant revenue-generating potential, corruption, political interference, limited transparency, and ineffective institutional oversight continue to undermine efficient tax administration and public finance management. The reviewed studies collectively emphasize that sustainable economic development and improved public service delivery in Nigeria depend on comprehensive governance reforms that strengthen institutional capacity, enhance transparency, and enforce accountability in tax revenue management.

Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative research approach, relying on secondary data to analyze the misappropriation of tax revenue in Nigeria and the role of public sector governance in tax administration. The research follows a descriptive and explanatory design, where the descriptive aspect provides an overview of tax administration, while the explanatory component explores the underlying causes of revenue leakages and mismanagement.

The study relies exclusively on secondary data, sourced from government reports, academic literature, policy documents, audit reports, and media investigations. Government data from institutions

such as the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), and Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) will be analyzed to assess revenue trends and governance issues. In addition, published journal articles, books, and policy papers on taxation, public finance, and governance will provide theoretical and empirical insights. Budget reports, financial statements, and audit findings from both the Nigerian government and international organizations, including the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, will be reviewed to evaluate revenue leakages and mismanagement. Investigative journalism from reputable media outlets will also be examined to understand contemporary issues related to tax fraud, corruption, and governance failures.

The study collects financial reports, statistical data, and policy documents related to Nigeria's tax system from 2020 to 2024. A combination of content analysis and trend analysis will be employed to interpret financial data, examine tax revenue performance, and identify patterns of misappropriation. Comparative analysis will also be conducted, comparing Nigeria's tax governance framework with those of other developing economies to highlight weaknesses and potential areas for reform. By relying on secondary data, this research ensures objectivity and comprehensiveness in assessing public sector governance and tax revenue mismanagement in Nigeria.

The Impact of Public Sector Governance on the Misappropriation of Tax Revenue in Nigeria

Public sector governance plays a crucial role in determining the efficiency, transparency, and accountability of tax revenue management

in Nigeria. The extent to which governance structures uphold ethical financial practices and enforce strict regulations significantly influences the rate of misappropriation of public funds. In Nigeria, weak public sector governance has been a major factor in the diversion and misuse of tax revenue, leading to widespread corruption, inadequate service delivery, and poor economic development.

A fundamental aspect of public sector governance is the establishment of legal and institutional frameworks that regulate tax collection and expenditure. Agencies such as the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) are mandated to ensure compliance with tax policies and prevent financial misconduct. However, despite these institutions, systemic corruption within government agencies has allowed tax revenue to be misappropriated through fraudulent practices such as embezzlement, ghost worker schemes, inflated contracts, and diversion of funds meant for public projects (ICPC, 2022). According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023), Nigeria generated approximately ₦10.1 trillion in tax revenue in 2022, yet a significant portion of these funds failed to translate into infrastructural and social development due to leakages in the system.

One of the key weaknesses in Nigeria's public sector governance is poor financial accountability and weak enforcement of anti-corruption laws. Budget tracking mechanisms are often ineffective, allowing public officials to engage in financial mismanagement with minimal consequences. Reports from Transparency International (2023) indicate that Nigeria ranked among the lowest in its Corruption Perception Index, highlighting the persistent issues of bribery, tax evasion, and weak institutional controls. Additionally, political interference further

weakens governance structures, as top government officials often manipulate financial regulations to protect corrupt individuals from prosecution.

Another major challenge in public sector governance is lack of transparency in tax administration. While technology-driven reforms such as the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIIS) and Treasury Single Account (TSA) have been introduced to reduce fraud, their implementation has been undermined by insider abuse. For example, the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC, 2022) reported that fraudulent tax practices, including unauthorized tax waivers and underreporting of revenue collections, have cost Nigeria billions of naira annually.

The misappropriation of tax revenue in Nigeria has severe consequences for economic development, public service delivery, and citizen trust in government. When tax revenues are diverted for personal gain, critical sectors such as education, healthcare, and infrastructure suffer from chronic underfunding. This, in turn, exacerbates poverty and inequality, as the government fails to provide essential services despite the substantial revenues generated through taxation. Furthermore, the lack of transparency and accountability discourages taxpayers from complying with tax obligations, thereby reducing overall government revenue and increasing reliance on external borrowing.

To mitigate the misappropriation of tax revenue, strengthening public sector governance is imperative. Key recommendations include enhancing financial transparency through digital monitoring systems, enforcing strict anti-corruption laws, improving the independence of

financial regulatory agencies, and adopting international best practices in tax administration. Countries with strong governance structures, such as Rwanda and Botswana, have demonstrated that institutional reforms, coupled with political will, can significantly reduce corruption and improve tax revenue utilization.

The effectiveness of public sector governance directly impacts the extent of tax revenue misappropriation in Nigeria. Weak governance structures have facilitated widespread corruption and financial leakages, undermining economic growth and public trust in government institutions. Strengthening accountability mechanisms, enforcing strict anti-corruption laws, and ensuring transparency in tax administration are critical steps toward improving Nigeria's public financial management and reducing tax revenue misappropriation.

Assessing the Effectiveness of the PAYE System in Revenue Generation in Nigeria

The Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) system is a critical component of Nigeria's tax administration, designed to ensure the systematic deduction of personal income tax from employees' salaries before payment. The PAYE system serves as a major revenue stream for the government, particularly for state and federal tax authorities, and contributes to funding public services such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure. However, despite its importance, the effectiveness of the PAYE system in revenue generation remains a subject of debate due to several challenges, including tax evasion, weak enforcement, and administrative inefficiencies.

One of the key strengths of the PAYE system is its predictability and consistency in revenue collection. Since tax is deducted at the source before salaries are paid to employees, it minimizes the risks of tax evasion that are common in other forms of taxation. The system ensures a steady inflow of tax revenue to the government, reducing reliance on unpredictable or voluntary tax compliance. According to the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS, 2023), PAYE contributed a significant portion of Nigeria's total ₦10.1 trillion tax revenue in 2022, underscoring its role as a stable revenue source.

Despite its contributions, the effectiveness of the PAYE system in Nigeria is hindered by several structural and administrative challenges. One of the most pressing issues is the informal economy, which constitutes a large portion of Nigeria's workforce. Many businesses operate outside the formal tax net, making it difficult for tax authorities to enforce PAYE deductions. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023) estimates that over 65% of Nigeria's labor force is engaged in informal employment, meaning a significant number of income earners do not contribute to PAYE tax revenue. This limits the tax base and places a disproportionate burden on the formally employed population.

Another challenge is tax evasion and underreporting of income by employers. Some private sector employers manipulate salary structures to reduce taxable income, while others fail to remit deducted PAYE taxes to the appropriate tax authorities. Reports from the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC, 2022) highlight cases where companies deduct PAYE taxes from employees but divert the funds instead of remitting them to the government. This fraudulent practice leads to substantial revenue losses and undermines the effectiveness of the system.

Additionally, weak enforcement mechanisms and administrative inefficiencies have further reduced the effectiveness of the PAYE system in Nigeria. Tax collection agencies often lack the technological infrastructure and manpower needed to track tax compliance effectively. Although digital tax payment systems have been introduced, corruption and bureaucratic bottlenecks continue to hamper enforcement efforts. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC, 2023) has noted that loopholes in the enforcement of PAYE regulations contribute to revenue leakages and tax fraud.

To enhance the effectiveness of the PAYE system in revenue generation, several reforms are necessary. First, broadening the tax base by integrating informal sector workers into the tax system can significantly increase revenue. This can be achieved by offering incentives for voluntary tax compliance, implementing simplified tax regimes for small businesses, and leveraging digital payment systems to track earnings. Second, strengthening enforcement mechanisms through improved tax audits, stricter penalties for non-compliance, and enhanced digital monitoring can help reduce tax fraud and revenue leakages. Third, enhancing transparency and accountability in tax administration by ensuring that PAYE funds are effectively utilized for public services will encourage compliance and build trust in the tax system.

While the PAYE system remains a vital mechanism for revenue generation in Nigeria, its effectiveness is significantly undermined by tax evasion, administrative inefficiencies, and the dominance of the informal economy. These challenges limit the system's ability to maximize tax collection and ensure fiscal sustainability. Addressing these issues through comprehensive policy reforms, stricter

enforcement measures, and the adoption of technological innovations will enhance the efficiency of the PAYE system, ultimately strengthening Nigeria's overall tax revenue framework.

Recent data from the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) underscores the growing importance of tax revenue in Nigeria's economic stability. As shown in Table 1, total tax collections have increased substantially over the years, rising from ₦4.95 trillion in 2020 to ₦21.6 trillion in 2024. Notably, in 2024, the FIRS set a revenue target of ₦19.4 trillion but surpassed expectations by collecting ₦21.6 trillion, achieving 112% of the target and reflecting a remarkable 76% increase from the previous year (Federal Inland Revenue Service, 2024). This impressive growth highlights the potential of tax administration reforms and enforcement strategies to improve revenue collection. However, sustained progress requires ongoing efforts to curb revenue leakages, promote transparency, and enhance taxpayer compliance.

Table 1: Trend in Total Tax Revenue in Nigeria (2020–2024)

Year	Total Tax Revenue (₦ Trillion)
2020	4.95
2021	6.40
2022	10.10
2023	12.37
2024	21.60

Source: Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), 2024

Table 1 shows a consistent upward trend in total tax revenue over the period under review. Tax revenue more than quadrupled between 2020 and 2024, indicating improved tax administration, expanded tax base, and stronger enforcement mechanisms. The sharp increase recorded in

2024 reflects intensified revenue mobilization efforts and administrative reforms.

Table 2: PAYE Contribution and Structural Challenges in Nigeria

Indicator	Evidence / Observation	Source
PAYE contribution to total tax revenue (2022)	Significant share of ₦10.1 trillion total revenue	FIRS (2023)
Size of informal workforce	Over 65% of labour force	NBS (2023)
PAYE-related revenue leakages	Payroll fraud, ghost workers, non-remittance	ICPC (2022)
Enforcement weaknesses	Limited digital tracking, manpower constraints	EFCC (2023)

Source: Compiled from FIRS, NBS, ICPC, and EFCC Reports

Table 2 highlights that although PAYE remains a stable and predictable source of revenue, its effectiveness is constrained by structural factors, particularly the dominance of the informal sector and weak enforcement capacity. High levels of informal employment significantly reduce the PAYE tax base, while payroll fraud and non-remittance further undermine revenue realization.

Table 3: FIRS Revenue Target and Performance (2024)

Indicator	Amount (₦ Trillion)
Revenue Target	19.40
Actual Revenue Collected	21.60
Performance Rate	112%
Year-on-Year Growth	76%

Source: Federal Inland Revenue Service (2024)

Table 3 shows that FIRS exceeded its 2024 revenue target by a substantial margin, achieving 112% performance. This outcome suggests that tax administration reforms and improved compliance measures can yield significant revenue gains when effectively implemented.

The evidence presented across the tables demonstrates that Nigeria's tax revenue performance has improved significantly in recent years, with PAYE remaining a crucial component of revenue generation. However, despite overall growth in tax collections, the PAYE system's effectiveness is weakened by a narrow formal tax base, widespread informal employment, administrative inefficiencies, and corruption-related leakages. While improved enforcement and digitalization have contributed to increased revenue, sustaining this progress requires targeted reforms aimed at integrating the informal sector, strengthening payroll audits, and enhancing transparency in tax remittance and utilization.

Misappropriation and Misuse of Tax Revenue in Nigeria

The misappropriation and misuse of tax revenue in Nigeria remain significant challenges that undermine economic development and good governance. Despite substantial tax collections, corruption, financial leakages, and inefficiencies in public sector management have led to widespread diversion of funds, depriving citizens of essential services such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure (BudgIT, 2023).

Forms of Misappropriation and Misuse of Tax Revenue

One of the primary ways tax revenue is misappropriated is through embezzlement and diversion of funds by public officials. Government agencies responsible for managing tax revenue often engage in corrupt practices, including fraudulent contracts and illegal transfer of funds into private accounts. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission

(EFCC, 2023) reported multiple cases where tax revenues were stolen through inflated government expenditures and fraudulent procurement processes.

Additionally, the misallocation of tax revenue to non-essential projects further exacerbates the problem. Instead of funding critical sectors, tax revenue is often directed toward projects that do not directly benefit the public but serve political interests. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023) noted that while Nigeria generates trillions of naira annually from tax revenue, mismanagement has resulted in poor infrastructure development and declining public service quality.

Another widespread issue is ghost worker fraud, where government payrolls are manipulated to include non-existent employees. The Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC, 2022) found that fraudulent salary payments amounting to billions of naira were made to individuals who were not actually working for the government. This fraudulent practice depletes tax revenue that could otherwise be used for national development.

Furthermore, tax evasion and revenue leakages significantly reduce the amount of tax revenue available for public use. Corrupt officials often grant illegal tax waivers to businesses and individuals in exchange for bribes, thereby reducing the amount of tax collected (Federal Inland Revenue Service [FIRS], 2023). The World Bank (2023) estimated that Nigeria loses billions annually due to unremitted tax revenue and financial fraud in tax administration.

Impact of Tax Revenue Misappropriation

The misuse of tax revenue has severe consequences for Nigeria's economic and social development. One of the most notable effects is

the decline in public service delivery. Despite high tax revenue collections, many Nigerians lack access to basic services such as healthcare, education, and clean water due to financial mismanagement (BudGIT, 2023). This has resulted in widespread poverty and increased inequality.

Moreover, the misappropriation of tax revenue contributes to low public trust in government institutions. When citizens perceive that their taxes are being misused, they are less likely to comply with tax obligations, leading to increased tax evasion and lower government revenue. According to Transparency International (2023), Nigeria ranks among the lowest countries on the Corruption Perception Index, indicating deep-rooted issues in financial governance.

Additionally, the diversion and misuse of tax revenue hinder economic growth and development. Public funds that should be used to improve infrastructure, support businesses, and enhance productivity are instead stolen or wasted, reducing investment in critical sectors (World Bank, 2023). This discourages both local and foreign investors, further weakening the country's economy.

Efforts to Address the Issue

Several measures have been introduced to combat the misappropriation and misuse of tax revenue in Nigeria. The Treasury Single Account (TSA) policy was implemented to centralize government revenue collection and reduce financial leakages (FIRS, 2023). Additionally, the EFCC and ICPC have intensified their investigations into financial fraud and corruption cases, leading to multiple arrests and prosecutions (EFCC, 2023).

The introduction of digital tax collection systems has also improved transparency and accountability in tax administration. The FIRS (2023) has adopted electronic tax payment methods to reduce manual handling of tax revenue, thereby minimizing corruption risks. However, despite these efforts, challenges such as weak enforcement of anti-corruption laws, political interference, and lack of institutional independence continue to hinder meaningful progress (Transparency International, 2023).

The misappropriation and misuse of tax revenue in Nigeria remain significant obstacles to national development. While tax revenue is a critical source of government funding, widespread corruption, financial mismanagement, and weak oversight mechanisms continue to undermine its effectiveness. Strengthening anti-corruption institutions, enhancing financial transparency, and enforcing stricter legal penalties for tax fraud are essential to ensuring that tax revenue is properly utilized for the benefit of all citizens.

Evaluation of the Legal and Institutional Frameworks for Tax Revenue Management in Nigeria

The management of tax revenue in Nigeria is guided by various legal and institutional frameworks designed to ensure effective tax collection, allocation, and utilization. These frameworks include tax laws, regulatory bodies, and anti-corruption institutions aimed at promoting transparency, accountability, and efficiency in revenue management. However, challenges such as weak enforcement, corruption, and political interference continue to undermine their effectiveness.

Legal Framework for Tax Revenue Management

Nigeria's tax system is governed by multiple legislations that provide the legal foundation for tax collection and administration. Some of the key legal instruments include:

1. **The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999, as amended):** The constitution outlines the authority of different levels of government in tax administration. It assigns tax powers to the federal, state, and local governments, thereby defining revenue-sharing formulas and fiscal responsibilities (Federal Government of Nigeria, 1999).
2. **The Federal Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act, 2007:** This Act establishes the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) as the primary agency responsible for tax collection at the federal level. It provides the agency with legal backing to assess, collect, and account for tax revenue while enforcing compliance among taxpayers (FIRS, 2023).
3. **The Companies Income Tax Act (CITA), 2004:** CITA regulates the taxation of corporate entities in Nigeria, ensuring that businesses fulfill their tax obligations. It defines tax rates, exemptions, and penalties for non-compliance (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2004).
4. **The Personal Income Tax Act (PITA), 2011 (as amended):** This law governs the taxation of individuals, particularly through the Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) system. It ensures that income earners contribute to national revenue based on their earnings (FIRS, 2023).
5. **The Value Added Tax (VAT) Act, 1993 (as amended):** The VAT Act imposes a consumption tax on goods and services. It mandates businesses to collect VAT on behalf of the government and remit it to the appropriate authorities (NBS, 2023).

6. **The Fiscal Responsibility Act, 2007:** This law promotes transparency and accountability in public financial management, including tax revenue administration. It sets limits on government borrowing and requires periodic financial reporting (World Bank, 2023).
7. **The Finance Acts (2019-2023):** The series of Finance Acts introduced by the Nigerian government have modified existing tax laws to improve revenue generation and close tax loopholes. These reforms have adjusted tax rates, expanded the tax base, and introduced digital taxation (BudgIT, 2023).

Institutional Framework for Tax Revenue Management

Several institutions play critical roles in managing tax revenue in Nigeria. These agencies are tasked with tax collection, enforcement, and oversight to ensure effective revenue utilization. Some of the key institutions include:

1. **The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS):** As the principal tax collection agency, FIRS is responsible for administering federal taxes, ensuring compliance, and implementing tax policies (FIRS, 2023).
2. **The Joint Tax Board (JTB):** The JTB harmonizes tax administration across federal and state levels to reduce multiple taxation and improve efficiency (FIRS, 2023).
3. **State Boards of Internal Revenue (SBIRs):** Each state government operates a tax agency responsible for collecting personal income tax, land use charges, and other state-imposed levies (NBS, 2023).
4. **The Revenue Mobilization, Allocation, and Fiscal Commission (RMAFC):** This agency oversees the distribution of tax revenue among the three tiers of government and ensures equitable resource allocation (Transparency International, 2023).

5. **The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC):** These anti-corruption bodies investigate and prosecute financial crimes related to tax evasion, fraud, and misappropriation of revenue (EFCC, 2023; ICPC, 2022).

Challenges in the Legal and Institutional Frameworks

Despite the existence of comprehensive legal and institutional frameworks, several challenges hinder the efficient management of tax revenue in Nigeria:

- a) **Weak enforcement of tax laws:** Many businesses and individuals evade taxes due to poor enforcement mechanisms, resulting in revenue losses (World Bank, 2023).
- b) **Corruption and misappropriation:** Corrupt practices among tax officials and government agencies weaken revenue management and reduce public trust (EFCC, 2023).
- c) **Lack of coordination among tax agencies:** Overlapping functions between federal and state tax agencies create inefficiencies and revenue leakages (Transparency International, 2023).
- d) **Political interference:** High-level government officials often manipulate tax policies for personal or political gains, affecting fair revenue distribution (BudgIT, 2023).

Nigeria's legal and institutional frameworks for tax revenue management provide a structured approach to revenue collection and administration. However, weak enforcement, corruption, and poor coordination continue to undermine their effectiveness. Strengthening tax compliance mechanisms, enhancing financial transparency, and

ensuring accountability in tax administration are essential for optimizing Nigeria's tax revenue management.

The Impact of Poor Governance on Public Service Delivery in Nigeria

Governance is a crucial factor in determining the efficiency and effectiveness of public service delivery. In Nigeria, poor governance—characterized by corruption, lack of transparency, weak institutional frameworks, and inefficient public administration—has significantly hindered the provision of essential services such as healthcare, education, infrastructure, and security. These governance failures have led to widespread poverty, declining public trust, and slow economic development.

Corruption and Financial Mismanagement

Corruption remains a fundamental challenge to effective public service delivery in Nigeria. According to Arowolo and Lawal (2019), corruption is deeply entrenched in Nigeria's public sector, leading to the diversion of funds meant for public projects. The mismanagement of public resources through embezzlement, inflated contracts, and ghost worker schemes reduces the government's capacity to provide essential services. Olasupo and Idike (2020) argue that corruption in the public sector has resulted in infrastructural decay, poor healthcare services, and declining educational standards.

Inadequate Infrastructure and Poor Service Delivery

Poor governance has also resulted in inadequate infrastructure, making it difficult for citizens to access quality public services. Eboh and Ukah (2021) note that despite Nigeria's substantial revenue generation from oil and other sectors, infrastructural development remains substandard

due to misallocation of funds. Many roads, schools, and hospitals are either abandoned or in a state of disrepair due to weak project implementation strategies and lack of accountability. This situation forces many citizens to rely on expensive private services, deepening social inequalities.

Weak Institutional Capacity and Inefficiency

Public institutions in Nigeria often lack the technical capacity and resources required for effective service delivery. According to Agbodike, Igbokwe-Ibeto, and Nkah (2019), weak institutional capacity is a major factor behind inefficient public administration. Many government agencies suffer from bureaucratic delays, lack of proper coordination, and an absence of performance monitoring mechanisms. These inefficiencies lead to delays in project execution and poor service outcomes, further reducing public trust in governance.

Deterioration in Healthcare Services

Nigeria's healthcare sector has been severely affected by poor governance. Despite the annual budgetary allocations, the healthcare system continues to suffer from inadequate medical facilities, shortage of qualified personnel, and poor working conditions. Okafor and Onyishi (2020) highlight that funds allocated to the health sector are often misappropriated, leaving public hospitals in deplorable conditions. This has led to high maternal and child mortality rates, increased medical tourism, and an overreliance on expensive private healthcare services.

Decline in Educational Standards

Poor governance has also negatively impacted the education sector in Nigeria. Odukoya (2018) points out that corruption, lack of funding,

and poor policy implementation have led to a decline in educational standards. Many public schools and universities suffer from overcrowded classrooms, outdated curricula, and frequent strikes by lecturers and teachers due to unpaid salaries. The inability of the government to adequately fund the education sector has resulted in low-quality education and reduced employability of graduates.

Worsening Security Challenges

Security challenges in Nigeria have been exacerbated by poor governance. Ibrahim and Sani (2021) argue that mismanagement of security funds, corruption in the procurement of defense equipment, and weak law enforcement institutions have led to increased crime rates, insurgency, and kidnappings. Poor governance in the security sector has made it difficult for law enforcement agencies to effectively combat threats such as Boko Haram, banditry, and herdsman attacks, leading to widespread insecurity and displacement of citizens.

Erosion of Public Trust in Government

Another major impact of poor governance is the erosion of public trust in government institutions. Citizens lose confidence in the government when they perceive that public resources are being misused and that corruption goes unpunished. According to Ujo (2020), low public trust in government institutions discourages civic engagement, reduces tax compliance, and fosters political apathy. This lack of confidence weakens democratic processes and makes governance less effective.

Economic Stagnation and Underdevelopment

Poor governance has long-term negative effects on Nigeria's economic development. Mismanagement of public funds, lack of investment in critical sectors, and policy inconsistencies have discouraged both local

and foreign investments. Abubakar and Bala (2019) note that weak governance structures hinder economic diversification and sustainable growth. The inability of the government to create a stable economic environment has resulted in high unemployment rates, inflation, and persistent poverty.

The impact of poor governance on public service delivery in Nigeria is evident across multiple sectors. Corruption, financial mismanagement, weak institutional capacity, and lack of accountability continue to hinder the provision of essential services. Addressing these challenges requires stronger governance reforms, stricter anti-corruption measures, and improved resource management. Without significant policy interventions, Nigeria will continue to struggle with inefficient public service delivery and slow economic development.

Recommendations for Improving Transparency and Accountability in Tax Revenue Management in Nigeria

Effective tax revenue management is crucial for national development, as it ensures that public funds are collected and allocated efficiently to support infrastructure, healthcare, education, and other essential services. However, Nigeria has struggled with issues of tax evasion, mismanagement, and corruption, which have undermined public trust in the tax system. To address these challenges, the following recommendations should be implemented to improve transparency and accountability in tax revenue management.

Strengthening Legal and Institutional Frameworks

A robust legal framework is essential for enforcing tax laws and ensuring accountability. The Nigerian government should strengthen existing tax laws and introduce stricter penalties for tax fraud and misappropriation of funds. Additionally, tax institutions such as the

Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) should be given greater autonomy to function independently, free from political interference. Strengthening institutions will enhance their ability to enforce tax compliance and prevent revenue leakages (Ofoegbu & Omoju, 2019).

Enhancing Digitalization and Automation of Tax Systems

The integration of digital technology in tax collection can significantly reduce human interference and corruption. Implementing automated tax collection systems, such as the e-Tax platform, can help track payments, prevent fraudulent practices, and ensure real-time monitoring of revenue inflows (Adebisi & Gbegi, 2020). Digitalization also improves tax compliance by simplifying the payment process and reducing the bureaucratic challenges faced by taxpayers.

Establishing an Independent Revenue Monitoring Agency

An independent tax revenue monitoring agency should be established to oversee the collection, allocation, and utilization of tax funds. This agency should consist of representatives from civil society organizations, financial experts, and anti-corruption bodies. It should have the authority to audit government tax agencies, investigate irregularities, and publish reports on revenue performance and expenditure (Ogbuagu & Ibe, 2021).

Implementing Transparent Budgeting and Public Disclosure Policies

Public access to information on tax revenue collection and expenditure is vital for transparency. The government should mandate the publication of tax revenue reports, budget allocations, and expenditures on official platforms. This practice will enable the public to track how

tax funds are being used and hold public officials accountable (Akintoye & Tashie, 2019).

Strengthening Anti-Corruption Agencies

Corruption in tax revenue management remains a major concern in Nigeria. Strengthening anti-corruption agencies such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) will help investigate and prosecute tax-related fraud cases. These agencies should be given the resources and legal backing to enforce compliance and recover stolen tax funds (Ojo, 2020).

Encouraging Citizen Participation and Whistleblower Protection

The Nigerian government should encourage public involvement in tax governance by promoting citizen participation in budget formulation and tax allocation decisions. The Whistleblower Protection Policy should be reinforced to safeguard individuals who expose tax fraud and corruption in revenue management (Olanrewaju & Falade, 2022). Providing financial incentives and legal protection to whistleblowers will encourage more people to report cases of financial mismanagement.

Capacity Building and Training for Tax Officials

Building the capacity of tax officials through continuous training and development is essential for efficient tax administration. Training programs should focus on ethical tax practices, modern revenue collection techniques, and financial accountability (Eze & Okonkwo, 2021). Strengthening the professionalism of tax administrators will improve efficiency, reduce loopholes, and minimize corruption in the tax system.

Enhancing transparency and accountability in tax revenue management requires a comprehensive approach that includes legal reforms, digitalization, independent monitoring, public disclosure, anti-corruption measures, and citizen engagement. Implementing these strategies will not only improve tax compliance but also ensure that collected revenues are used for the benefit of the Nigerian people. A transparent and accountable tax system will foster economic growth, strengthen public trust, and enhance national development.

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